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Strategic Educational Management, Leadership Practices and Artificial Intelligence (AI) for Achieving Educational Objectives of Secondary Education in Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper examines the strategic educational management, leadership practices and Artificial Intelligence (AI) for achieving the educational objectives of secondary education in Nigeria. The paper utilized secondary data sourced from online and print publications by reviewing articles on Artificial Intelligence and Strategic Management and Leadership Practices for achieving the educational objectives of secondary education in Nigeria. The paper presents a review of the strategic management process for planning, implementing and evaluating the goals and objectives of secondary education in Nigeria, the applications of Artificial Intelligence that can enhance educational management, the importance of AI in educational management, the challenges and barriers of integrating AI in the secondary educational system, and the benefits of AI in secondary education in Nigeria. The paper underscores that without AI, personalization learning experiences for students, providing immediate responses and automating administrative tasks will not be achieved in schools. The paper concludes that AI has an enormous capacity to improve educational management; however, it must be deployed with heed and prudence. Based on these insights, the paper recommends that the Nigerian government should implement AI in schools to address challenges students are facing by leveraging AI educators to offer tailored instructions to identify students' strengths and weaknesses.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Educational Management, Strategic Management, Secondary Education

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Strategic Educational Management, Leadership Practices and Artificial Intelligence for Achieving Educational Objectives of Secondary Education in Nigeria

Introduction

Education in Nigeria and all over the world has gone beyond teaching and learning within the four walls of the classrooms. A child could be educated from his experiences outside the school. Parents can also impart in their children some basic societal norms, ethics, and good conduct inherent in their societies (Akpan, 2011). Education as a social institution through which a society's children are taught basic academic knowledge, acquire skills, and cultural norms, is an inseparable part of human life. Without it, human life is incomplete, painful, and hopeless. It stands for deliberate instructions or training. In the past, teachers who were knowledgeable in the teaching and learning process have done extremely well in inspiring and imparting the required knowledge that sustains the child to survive in society and also contribute meaningfully to the nation's economy.

Artificial intelligence (AI) refers to the creation of computer systems capable of performing tasks that historically only a human being could do, such as reasoning, making decisions, or solving problems. It is also the mechanical stimulation of human intelligence processes, especially computer systems. Specific application of AI includes expert systems, natural language processing, speech recognitions, machine vision, etc. Generally, artificial intelligence systems can achieve tasks that are universally associated with human reasoning, such as interpreting speech, playing games and identifying patterns. They typically learn how to do so by processing massive amounts of data, looking for patterns to model in their own decision-making. Naija.S. (2024). Artificial Intelligence (AI), as emphasized by the Minister of Education on the International

Day of Education, underscores the role of AI in shaping the future of education. He stressed the importance of tools like virtual reality, gamification, and AI-driven grading systems, which transform the learning experience for students and teachers. Dr Alausa outlined a strategic roadmap to ensure responsible AI integration in education. This includes: incorporating AI literacy with necessary skills, and fostering partnerships with global stakeholders. The Federal Ministry of Education, through its commitment to harnessing the potential of AI to enhance education in Nigeria, reaffirms its commitment to innovation and responsible AI integration. The ministry aims to create a more accessible, efficient and innovative learning environment for all Nigerians. Anyanwu (2025).

Secondary school education in Nigeria is the second level of education. This level of education was established to serve as a gap between primary education and tertiary education (Akpan, 2011). According to FRN (2013), it is the education that is received after primary education and before tertiary education, and it is meant to provide the requisite skills and knowledge to make their products ready and/or self-reliant for further studies. This stage of education is a crucial tier in the hierarchy of education in Nigeria, and it is intended for pupils between the ages of 11-17. Secondary education in Nigeria is made up of junior basic and senior basic education, which takes three years each to complete so both programs run for a period of six years. At each level, there is an administrator known as the school principal. Although in private secondary schools, one administrator is usually in charge of both programs. In some secondary school settings, countries have

started to design and implement curricula to develop their students with artificial intelligence (AI) literacy skills that support their future studies and careers (Ng et al., 2023b; UNESCO, 2022). On this premise, this article highlights the strategic educational management, leadership practices and artificial intelligence (AI) for achieving the educational objectives of secondary education in Nigeria.

Literature Review.

Concept of Strategic Management

Strategic management is the process of planning, implementing, and evaluating the goals and objectives of an organization to achieve long-term success and sustainable competitive benefits of the educational aims/objectives (Eliza, 2024). It involves analyzing the internal and external factors that affect the organization, setting clear objectives, formulating strategies to achieve those objectives and allocating resources effectively. Strategic management also involves monitoring and adjusting strategies in response to changes in the business environment. It is a crucial aspect of organizational leadership, guiding decision-making at all levels (Eliza, 2024). Strategy is a detailed blueprint for any organization towards proper administration and the achievement of success. As such, every organization, including schools, maps out plans to enable it to succeed. When organizations do not plan well, such organizations are bound to fail. Hence, there is a need for strategic management. Strategic management comprises the set of decisions and actions that result in the formulation and implementation of plans designed to achieve a firm's objectives (Monday et al., 2015). It is the process of making decisions, planning, coordinating and taking some actions by management staff in the school in order to achieve set goals and objectives. The

management staff often makes decisions at the top, but these decisions are of little use unless they are acted upon. Schools must take the necessary actions to implement their strategies in every area, including the area of security. These actions involve long-term, future-oriented, complex decision-making and require a considerable measure of resources. Olaitan (2005) explained strategic planning as that part of corporate planning which involves the assessment of needs, the identification of desired outcomes and the assessment of various programmes, initiatives and resources towards the attainment of set objectives. Therefore, strategic planning is concerned with shaping the organization to the right path. In this context, the application and inclusiveness of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in the school curriculum towards the achievement of goals or objectives and effective strategies have to be clear, specific, measurable, attainable, realistic and time-bound objectives which are relevant to the needs of the educational system in Nigeria.

The Concept of Artificial Intelligence

The Nigerian educational system is poised for a revolution with the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI). AI has the potential to enhance learning, improve student outcomes, and increase access to quality education. In Nigeria, AI-powered adaptive learning can help address the challenge of inadequate teachers in rural areas; AI-driven chatbots can provide personalized learning experiences for students, while intelligent tutoring systems can offer real-time feedback and assessment (Naija, 2024). AI revolutionizes education by personalizing learning experiences for students, providing real-time feedback, and automating administrative tasks. Implementing AI in Nigerian schools can address challenges such as large class size, insufficient resources, and varying student needs. By leveraging AI, educators can offer tailored instruction, identify students'

strengths and weaknesses more effectively, and track progress accurately. Exploring AI's potential in Nigerian education reveals promising opportunities for enhancing learning outcomes and administrative efficiency. By integrating AI into the education system, Nigeria can equip its students with the skills and knowledge needed to thrive in an increasingly digital and interconnected world. Embracing AI in education is not just a technological advancement; it is a step towards building a more equitable and progressive society. Naija.S. (2024).

In many cases, human beings supervise an AI's learning process, reinforcing good decisions and discouraging bad ones. But some AI systems are designed to learn without supervision. Artificial intelligence enables educators to create and update content more efficiently and effectively, ensuring learning materials are always up to date and relevant. For the students, it helps them to stay informed on the latest developments around the world and prepares them for future challenges. Artificial intelligence (AI) is an advanced technology that simulates human intelligence processes using machine learning algorithms, neural networks, and natural language processing (NLP). AI is transforming various industries, including healthcare, finance, and manufacturing. In recent years, AI has also made inroads into the education sector, particularly in educational management. AI can help improve the learning process, enhance student outcomes, and automate administrative tasks. The application of AI in educational management is still in its early stages, but it has already shown promising results. For instance, AI-powered learning systems can personalize the learning experience for students, provide real-time feedback, and detect potential problems early. Similarly, AI can help educators identify student strengths and weaknesses,

enabling them to tailor their teaching methods accordingly. Naija.S. (2024).

However, AI in educational management also raises several ethical, legal, and social issues. For example, the use of AI in education can lead to potential biases and discrimination, raise privacy concerns, and impact the labour market. Therefore, it is crucial to evaluate the application of AI in educational management carefully and to incorporate it into our secondary education.

Concept of Educational Management

Educational management refers to the process of planning, organizing, directing, and controlling resources (human, financial, and physical) within an educational institution to achieve specific goals and objectives. It involves various activities such as curriculum development, teacher training, student assessment, and school budgeting. Educational management is essential for ensuring that educational institutions run efficiently and effectively to provide quality education to students. Bush and Glover (2014) maintain that educational management is an important field of study that helps educational institutions to meet their goals and objectives. Igbokwe (2023) states that effective educational management requires the use of appropriate management techniques and tools, such as strategic planning, performance management, and financial management.

A very important aspect of educational management is leadership. Leithwood et al. (2004) hold that effective leadership is critical for the success of educational institutions. The authors argue that effective leaders create a vision for the institution, establish clear goals and objectives, develop and support a talented staff, and create a positive school culture. Teacher development is another crucial aspect of educational management. Darling-Hammond et al. (2009) argue that teacher development is essential for improving

student achievement. The authors suggest that teacher development programs should focus on improving instructional strategies, providing ongoing support and feedback, and promoting collaboration among teachers.

In addition, student assessment is a key component of educational management. For Black and William (1998), assessment is essential for improving student learning. The authors argue that assessment should be formative, ongoing, and integrated into the teaching and learning process. Finally, budgeting and resource management are also critical aspects of educational management. It is the view of Branson et al. (2002) that effective budgeting and resource management can help educational institutions to allocate resources efficiently and effectively to achieve their goals and objectives. Igbokwe C.I (2023).

Importance of AI in Educational Management

Generally, AI has the potential to transform various aspects of education, including educational management. Here are some of how AI can be important in educational management, as ascertained by Igbokwe (2023)

Personalized Learning:

AI can help in creating personalized learning experiences for students by analyzing their learning styles and abilities. This will allow educators to customize their teaching methods, curricula and materials to meet the individual needs of each student. AI can be used to create personalized learning experiences for students. AI-based learning systems can analyze student data, such as their learning style, pace, and preferences, and then provide them with tailored learning experiences. This can lead to improved engagement, motivation, and ultimately, better learning outcomes (Oztok et al., 2019).

Intelligent Tutoring:

The use of artificial intelligence (AI) in educational management can improve intelligent tutoring systems (ITS) by providing personalized and adaptive feedback to students (VanLehn, 2011). For example, AI-powered ITS can collect and analyze data on student performance, learning patterns, and engagement levels to provide individualized support and interventions (O'Neil et al, 2019). Additionally, AI can enable the ITS to adjust the difficulty of the content based on the student's proficiency level, which can promote mastery learning and increase motivation (Woolf, 2010). AI-powered intelligent tutoring systems can provide immediate feedback to students, identify knowledge gaps and suggest suitable learning strategies. This can be particularly beneficial for students who need extra support in their learning.

Streamlining Administrative Tasks: AI can be used to improve the efficiency of administrative tasks in educational institutions. AI-powered systems can automate routine tasks, such as grading, scheduling, and record-keeping, freeing up educators' time to focus on more impactful work, such as lesson planning and student engagement (Oztok & Zingaro, 2019). Educational institutions have to deal with a lot of administrative tasks, such as scheduling, grading, and record-keeping. AI can automate many of these tasks, freeing up educators' time to focus on teaching and supporting students.

Enhancing Learning Outcomes:

Recent research suggests that the application of artificial intelligence (AI) in educational management can help to improve learning outcomes for students (Gupta, 2020). For example, AI-powered tutoring systems can provide personalized feedback and adaptive learning experiences that are tailored to each student's needs and learning style (O'Neil et. al, 2019). AI can also be used to analyze large amounts of student data, such as assessment

scores and behavioural patterns, to identify areas where students may be struggling and provide targeted interventions (Zawacki-Richter et. al, 2014). Overall, the integration of AI in educational management has the potential to enhance teaching and learning practices and improve student outcomes. Indeed, AI can help educators identify which teaching methods and materials are most effective in enhancing learning outcomes. This information can be used to refine and improve the curriculum, resulting in better student performance.

The use of AI in secondary education has several potential advantages. AI technologies have the ability to customize learning experiences. Tailoring them to the specific needs and learning preferences of each learner. This flexibility facilitates the accommodation of a wide range of student capabilities and promotes a more inclusive educational setting. Furthermore, AI-driven technologies enhance dynamic and captivating learning experiences by integrating simulations, virtual experiments, and practical applications. This not only improves students' understanding of certain subjects but also ignites curiosity and excitement for the subject. Moreover, AI has the capability to promptly offer feedback to both students and teachers, facilitating quick intervention and adaptation of teaching tactics (Ross et. al, 2018). This feedback loop enhances the efficiency and effectiveness of the teaching and learning process.

In Nigeria, where access to high-quality education may vary, the potential advantages of AI in secondary education in certain areas narrow educational disparities, enhance educational achievement, and equip students for a future when technology is more integrated into every part of life. Integrating AI in teaching and learning in Nigeria is not just about improving educational procedures,

but also about strategically equipping students for a future where technology and innovation play a crucial role in social advancement and wealth. Adesina (2024).

Challenges and Barriers of Integrating AI in the Secondary Educational System.

There are many challenges to the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in secondary schools in Nigeria. The barriers include;

- Infrastructural restrictions in several educational institutions nationwide
- The lack of sufficient access to technology, such as PCs or tablets, impedes the efficient implementation of AI-powered instructional aides (Aina et al., 2023). In addition,
- The irregular provision of electricity and insufficient internet access in many schools provide substantial challenges, promoting allocation of more resources towards education infrastructure, fostering partnerships with both public and commercial sectors, and creating AI apps that can function without an internet connection or with limited bandwidth are viable methods to address these infrastructure difficulties.
- Preparation of competent teachers to integrate AI into the educational system, several educators may lack enough training in using AI tools in the classroom, impeding their capacity to successfully harness new technology.
- Another obstacle is resistance to change. This is a result of being familiar with the efficacy of AI. It is necessary to execute extensive training programmes, cooperate with educational institutions for ongoing professional growth, and create mentoring programmes to allow the exchange of information among educators (Adeyemi, 2020).

Benefits of AI in Secondary Education in Nigeria.

In Nigeria, AI-powered adaptive learning systems can help address the challenge of inadequate teachers in rural areas. AI-driven chatbots can provide personalized learning experiences for students, while intelligent tutoring systems can offer real-time feedback and assessment (Lin et al., 2020)

1. Enhanced Learning Outcomes.

AI-powered educational platforms can provide personalized learning experiences, tailored to individuals' needs of students. This can lead to improved learning outcomes, as students can learn at their own pace and according to their learning style, which can result in better retention and understanding of the content.

2. Increased Access to Education

Virtual classrooms powered by AI can provide access to quality education for students in remote or underserved areas, where physical classrooms may be limited or nonexistent. This can help bridge the gap in educational opportunities between urban and rural areas and provide access to education for marginalized populations, ultimately increasing overall literacy rates and educational attainment in Nigeria.

3. AI tools can assist teachers in creating more effective instructional strategies by analyzing data on student performance, identifying areas where additional support may be needed, and suggesting relevant teaching materials. This can help teachers tailor their teaching methods to the specific needs of their students, resulting in improved teaching practices and better student outcomes.

4. Time and Cost Savings

Automated assessment using AI can save time and resources in the grading process, allowing teachers to provide timely feedback to students and focus on other important aspects of teaching. Virtual classrooms powered by

AI can also save costs associated with building physical infrastructure, and can reach a wider audience of students, potentially reducing the cost of education for many.

5. Enhanced Creativity and Critical Thinking.

AI-powered educational tools like QuillBot which is used in advanced paraphrasing functions, Grammar checker and Plagiarism checker, then, Owlift, this tool helps in complex concept simplification, AI Discussion Question Generator and interactive learning, also, Real-time Feedback tool, which helps in Vocabulary Enhancement, and Cross-Platform Accessibility this tools can foster creativity and critical thinking skills in students by providing opportunities for problem –solving, analysis, and interactive learning experiences can engage students in hands-on learning, allowing them to develop their creativity and critical thinking skills, which are essential for the workforce of the future. Lin et al. (2020).

Methodology

In search for literature on strategic management and leadership practices and artificial intelligence for achieving educational objectives of secondary education in Nigeria, peer-reviewed scholarly articles and conference papers published from 1998 to 2025 were included in this review. The AI articles were downloaded and reviewed by the researchers during the review. In this review, the majority of the articles (21) are conference papers, while the other seven are journal publications.

Conclusion

The impact of AI on secondary education is evident and significant. Ways of learning are changing, and traditional teaching methods are giving way to new, technology-based approaches. The challenge for educational communities and policymakers is creating regulations that allow for AI's controlled

development in education. In education, artificial intelligence (AI) is a powerful tool to support various aspects of the teaching and learning process. AI has the ability not only to automate many processes but also to personalize and adapt to the individual needs of students. From the perspective of inclusive education, which aims to create an environment that supports the participation of all students, the use of AI can bring significant benefits. Artificial intelligence enables the personalization of the teaching process, which means adapting teaching materials, pace, and teaching style to students' abilities and needs. Thanks to data analysis, AI can identify each student's strengths, allowing it to focus on developing specific skills. AI-based technologies have the potential to adapt to students' progress, offering them appropriate challenges as they acquire new skills. Adaptive learning allows for dynamic adjustments to curricula, which helps maintain student motivation and increases the effectiveness of the educational process. Thanks to advanced natural language processing algorithms, AI can recognize speech and text, which opens up new opportunities for students with various difficulties, including dyslexia or other reading problems. These tools can support the reading process by enabling access to educational content in a way tailored to individual needs. Artificial intelligence can support students through various assistive technologies, such as image recognition programs or unique applications that help with math tasks. These tools aim to eliminate barriers, enabling students with multiple difficulties to participate more fully in the educational process, enabling teachers to approach each student individually. However, at the same time, it is essential to supervise the development of these technologies and ensure their principle and safe use, minimizing impending risks. We hope this review will

inspire scholars, educators and government officers to begin the discussion on how to define, implement and strategize on how best AI should be inculcated in the school curricula.

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